

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

Living Hubs Design

Agroforestry Plan

27/03/2024

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Author(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elisabetta Meconcelli - Treedom - Tommaso Tusa - Treedom - Gianni Della Rocca - CNR - Pierluigi Paris - CNR - Javier Sánchez - Rancho - Federico Franciamore - S4G - Caroline Zaoui - NOVOBIOM - Theocharis Nazos - NTUA - Andriani Galani - NTUA - Pinelope Papadopoulou - NTUA - Tadej Stepisnik Perdih - NTUA - Simos Malamis - NTUA 		
Contact	e.meconcelli@treedom.net		
Reviewer	Valerio Roscani, Fondazione E. Amaldi		
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Introduction

Context

Within the INNO4CFIs project, the creation of several application sites for the technologies analyzed within it is planned. Sites called "Living Hub" (LH) are intended to create agroforestry areas for carbon farming purposes.

There will be 4 pilot projects with a minimum of 1.500 to a maximum of 3.000 trees.

Project site areas are:

- Tuscany, Italy
- Castilla y León, Spain
- Wallonia, Belgium
- Attica, Greece

In each site selected technologies developed in INNO4CFIs will be tested and the Tuscany site will be a reference area as all the technologies will be tested there.

This document sets for each site an agroforestry plan establishing, with local partners, experimental sites for tree planting, on agricultural lands, with specific association with agricultural activities (herbaceous crops or pasture for farmed grazing).

Sites have been selected, with a bottom-up approach, along with trees and crops selection appropriate to site conditions, according to the current climatic conditions and their possible evolution concerning climate change scenarios.

Treedom, CNR and Rancho are designing the agroforestry plan for the Italian and Spanish sites with the approximate (according to climatic events) first planting in March and April 2024. For the sites in Belgium and Greece, we will have the completion of all sites in March 2025. In this period project partners and stakeholders supporting the planting activities will be trained on the topic of agroforestry system management and maintenance.

EU and institutional framework

In February 2024 Council and Parliament agreed to establish an EU carbon removal certification framework.

To achieve its climate neutrality goals by 2050 besides the reduction of GHG emissions there is the need to compensate hard to abate residual emissions.

The proposal sets out a voluntary EU-wide framework to certify carbon removals generated in Europe. The aim is to foster innovative carbon removal technologies and sustainable carbon farming solutions, to do so it outlines criteria to define high-quality carbon removals and the process to monitor, report and verify the authenticity of these removals.¹

By 2026, the Commission is tasked with producing a report on the feasibility of certifying activities based on a pilot certification methodology.²

Carbon removal types of units are defined as:

In our Living Hubs, we will focus on **soil emission reduction from carbon farming**.

¹ climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/sustainable-carbon-cycles/carbon-removal-certification_en [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

² www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/02/20/climate-action-council-and-parliament-agree-to-establish-an-eu-carbon-removals-certification-framework/ [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

On sustainability for carbon farming, the co-legislators have added indications on how the sustainability objectives must be understood. In particular **carbon farming activity must always generate at least a biodiversity co-benefit** (including soil health and avoidance of land degradation).

Q.U.A.L.ITY criteria

The planting projects, among other activities, include the planting of new trees and CO₂ absorption activities in addition to the actual storage potential of the area.

The project respects the principles set out on 30 November 2022 by the European Commission in its [proposal for a regulation](#) to create a European Union framework for the voluntary certification of carbon removals.³

The proposal fits in with the EU's commitments to reduce emissions and become 'climate neutral' by 2050 included in the [Green Deal](#) and the objectives of the "[Fit for 55](#)" package, which foresees the reduction of net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% compared to 1990 levels. The regulation has the clear objective of promoting activities for the removal of atmospheric CO₂, this time also including the agricultural and forestry sectors, contributing to the target of 310 Mt of carbon removals by 2030 in the LULUCF (Land use, land use change, and forestry) sector.

The regulation aims to ensure transparency and credibility of the certification process and the carbon market by setting standards for the independent verification of removals and regulating the recognition of certification systems. The latter is undoubtedly an innovative element, as it will allow for the recognition of certification systems already in use in several European countries (e.g. Label Bas Carbone in France) if they comply with the four Q.U.A.L.ITY criteria:

1. QUantification (quantification): carbon absorption activities must be measured accurately and must produce unequivocal benefits;
2. Additionality: Absorption activities must go beyond what is required by law;
3. Long-term storage: certificates are linked to the duration of carbon storage, ensuring permanence;
4. sustainabillTY: Absorption activities must safeguard or contribute to sustainability objectives, such as the protection of water resources and biodiversity, among others.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/it/ip_22_7156 [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

In particular, criterion 4 expresses the need for activities aimed at carbon sequestration to also take into account other commitments in terms of sustainability. Indeed, activities are required to have a neutral or, better, positive impact in the following areas: mitigation and adaptation to climate change; protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems; sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources; transition to a circular economy; and pollution prevention and control. In addition, these actions should consider the criteria of the “Do Not Significant Harm” regulation.⁴

Agroforestry key concept

According to FAO-Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, “Agroforestry is a collective name for land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos, etc.) are deliberately used on the same land-management units as crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence.

In agroforestry systems, there are both ecological and economic interactions between the different components. Agroforestry can also be defined as a dynamic, ecologically based, natural resource management system that, through the integration of trees on farms and in the agricultural landscape, diversifies and sustains production for increased social, economic, and environmental benefits for land users at all levels. Agroforestry is crucial to smallholder farmers and other rural people because it can enhance their food supply, income and health. Agroforestry systems are multifunctional systems that can provide a wide range of economic, sociocultural, and environmental benefits.”⁵

Several criteria can be considered for establishing a classification of agroforestry systems:

- components: crops, trees, shrubs, pasture, animals, aquaculture, etc.;
- dominant land use: primarily agriculture or primarily forestry;
- spatial organisation: on boundaries, in strips, densely mixed (home gardens), sparsely mixed (most systems of trees with pasture);
- temporal arrangements: overlapping, separate;
- agro-ecological environment: tropical, boreal, humid, high land/low land, etc.;
- socio-economic management level (amounts of technological input and degree of commercialisation);

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/it/ip_22_7156 [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

⁵ <https://www.fao.org/forestry/agroforestry/80338/en/> [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

- function: productive (food, fodder, fuel wood), habitat (supporting biodiversity), regulating (climate, flood and drought prevention), cultural (recreation and landscape).⁶

FAO proposes three main types of agroforestry systems that are classified based on the type of components. The three main groups combine trees or woody shrubs, as the essential perennial component:

1. Silvopastoral systems combine forestry and grazing of domesticated animals on pastures, rangelands, or on-farm.
2. Agrisilvicultural systems are a combination of crops and trees, such as alley cropping or home gardens.
3. Agrosilvopastoral systems are illustrated by home gardens involving animals as well as scattered trees on croplands used for grazing after harvests.⁷

A 2018 study examining what role agroforestry plays in the fight against climate change and how it is promoted within the Common Agricultural Policy, identifies five basic spatial agroforestry practices:

- Silvopastoral: a combination of trees and shrubs with forage and animal production;
- Silvoarable: trees and shrubs intercropped with annual or perennial crops;
- Forest farming: forested areas used for the production or harvest of natural-standing speciality crops for medicinal, ornamental or culinary uses;
- Hedgerows, windbreaks and riparian buffer strips: lines of natural or planted perennial vegetation (tree/shrub) bordering croplands/pastures and water sources to protect livestock, crops, and/or soil and water quality;

⁶ Nair, P.K.R., Kumar, B.M., Nair, V.D. (2021). Classification of Agroforestry Systems. In: An Introduction to Agroforestry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75358-0_3

⁷ Agroforestry: Essential for Sustainable and Climate-Smart Land Use? - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Classification-of-agroforestry-systems-based-on-the-type-of-components-The-three-main_fig10_305773893 [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

- Home gardens or kitchen gardens: combining trees/shrubs with vegetable production⁸

Other criteria such as the system’s functional, socioeconomic, ecological management and technological characteristics were used to group the systems in a purpose-oriented manner.⁹ Below we provide a not exhaustive list of those criteria.

“Functional Classification” two basic characteristics of all agroforestry systems are production and protection.

1. Productive Agroforestry system refers to the production of those products and goods essential to meet society’s basic needs. Productive functions can be summarised:

2. Protective Agroforestry systems are those that mainly aim to protect the land, improve climate, mitigate water erosion, reduce wind, enhance soil fertility, provide shelter, and other benefits. Protective functions are as follows:¹⁰

“Socioeconomic Classification” based on socioeconomic consideration, the agroforestry system is classified as:

⁸ Mosquera-Losada, María Rosa & Santiago-Freijanes, José & Rois, Mercedes & Moreno, Gerardo & Herder, Michael & Vazquez, Jose Antonio & Ferreiro-Domínguez, Nuria & Pantera, Anastasia & Pisanelli, Andrea & Rigueiro-Rodríguez, Antonio. (2018). Agroforestry in Europe: a land management policy tool to combat climate change.

⁹ Nair, P.K.R., Kumar, B.M., Nair, V.D. (2021). Classification of Agroforestry Systems. In: An Introduction to Agroforestry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75358-0_3

¹⁰ Nair, P.K.R. Classification of agroforestry systems. Agroforest Syst 3, 97–128 (1985). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00122638>

- a. Subsistence Agroforestry system is one in which the use of land is directed toward satisfying basic needs and is managed by the owner or occupant and his/her family. Cash crops, including the sale of surplus commodities, may well be part of these systems but are only supplementary.
- b. Commercial Agroforestry system is a large-scale production on a commercial basis. The main aim is to sell the products.
- c. Intermediate Agroforestry system is the one intermediate between commercial and subsistence scale of production. It usually involves small and medium farms and the main features distinguishing it from the commercial and subsistence ones are holding size and level of economic prosperity¹¹

The Socioeconomic Agroforestry system may further be classified based on the Management and Technology used.

“Management Classification” within this broad category, several types of systems and practices can be identified depending on the role of the tree/shrub component.

- a. Intensively managed systems are agroforestry systems intensively managed for more production per unit area.
- b. Extensively managed system includes Shifting cultivation, Silvopasture, Pastoral silviculture, etc.¹²

“Technology Classification” considers the level of technology inputs used in the system. It refers to an innovation or improvement, usually through scientific intervention.¹³

- a. Low technology systems are primitive, as in shifting cultivation.
- b. High-technology system depends on modern technology for forest and agricultural crop production.
- c. Intermediate technology systems are between low and high technology systems. Most Agroforestry systems belong to this category.¹⁴

Agroforestry in Europe

The [Agforward](#) project, states that the area under agroforestry in the EU-27 is around 10.6 million ha, 3 equivalents to almost 9 % of the utilised agricultural area (or 3.6 % of the

¹¹ Nair, P.K.R., Kumar, B.M., Nair, V.D. (2021). Classification of Agroforestry Systems. In: An Introduction to Agroforestry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75358-0_3

¹² Idem 11

¹³ Nair, P.K.R., Kumar, B.M., Nair, V.D. (2021). Classification of Agroforestry Systems. In: An Introduction to Agroforestry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75358-0_3

¹⁴ <https://agriculturistmusa.com/classification-of-agroforestry-system/> [accessed 21 Feb, 2024]

territorial area). If reindeer husbandry is included in it, agroforestry covers 52 million ha. This land is under different forms of livestock agroforestry, and a smaller portion – 358.000 ha – is under arable agroforestry.¹⁵

Figure 1 Distribution of agroforestry in Europe. A) arable agroforestry, B) livestock agroforestry, C) high value tree agroforestry, and D) total extent of agroforestry¹⁶

¹⁵ Nair, P.K.R., Kumar, B.M., Nair, V.D. (2021). Classification of Agroforestry Systems. In: An Introduction to Agroforestry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75358-0_3

¹⁶ Current extent and stratification of agroforestry in the European Union - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Distribution-of-agroforestry-in-Europe-A-arable-agroforestry-B-livestock_fig1_315471872 [accessed 26 Mar, 2024]

Agroforestry benefits

Agroforestry systems provide several environmental and socio-economic benefits, in this paragraph, we outline those that the INNO4CFIs project find particularly relevant for the European Union communities.

<i>Environmental Benefits</i>	
<u>Mitigation</u>	It involves more biomass than conventional agriculture, it can store more carbon in plants and soils. By avoiding tillage, it prevents soil erosion and the subsequent release of CO2 into the atmosphere.
<u>Adaptation</u>	Shade provided by trees helps keep the local microclimate in check by retaining water in the soil, keeping temperatures lower and preserving humidity; agroforestry systems are very robust and can withstand extreme weather events.
<u>Biodiversity</u>	Agroforestry systems provide food, shelter and habitat for birds and insects, and pesticide applications that harm insect populations are reduced.
<u>Pest reduction</u>	Agroforestry systems contain more plant and animal species than conventional agriculture, they are more effective in controlling pests and harmful weeds.
<u>Soil protection</u>	As well as increasing the structural stability of the soil, tree roots can enhance water infiltration and improve water storage by increasing the number of soil pores. Macropores rapidly channel surplus surface water flow and allow air and moisture to move into the soil. In this way the risk of soil erosion is reduced; tree roots and trunks also act as physical barriers to reduce the surface flow of water and sediment.
<u>Soil remediation</u>	The role of agroforestry in rehabilitating polluted soils has been investigated, through exploiting the ability of trees to capture nutrients and pollutants.
<u>Soil biodiversity</u>	Agroforestry maintains and restores the topsoil with its organisms and nutrients; the soil is protected by a layer of dead organic materials that keeps water from evaporating and feeds the organisms living in the soil.
<u>Soil quality</u>	By promoting a closed system with internal recycling of nutrients, whereby nutrients are accessed from lower soil horizons by tree roots and returned to the soil through leaf fall, agroforestry systems enhance soil nutrient pools and turnover and reduce reliance on external inputs.
<u>Water management</u>	Agroforestry can reduce pollution from crops and grazed pastures, with tree strips located adjacent to water courses reducing nonpoint source water pollution from agricultural land in five key ways: Reducing surface runoff from fields; Filtering surface runoff; Filtering groundwater runoff; Reducing bank erosion; Filtering stream water.
<u>Animal Welfare</u>	Trees provide shelter from wind, cold and rain, and shade from the

	sun. They offer protection from predators and encourage natural behaviour such as foraging and scratching.
<u>Socioeconomic Benefits</u>	
<u>Agro productivity</u>	Agroforestry systems can lead to increased agricultural productivity as the combination of tree and crop systems can lead to a more efficient capture of resources, such as solar radiation or water, than separated tree or crop systems. However, this is not always the case in temperate zones.
<u>Pest & fertility control</u>	The need for external inputs, such as fertilisers or pesticides, is diminished, as soil fertility is improved, and pest infestation can be combated more naturally.
<u>Economic profit</u>	Economic studies of agroforestry systems have shown that financial benefits are a consequence of increasing the diversity and productivity of the systems which are influenced by market and price fluctuations of timber, livestock, and crops. In addition to the higher yield potentials of agroforestry, product diversification increases the potential for economic profits by providing annual and periodic revenues from multiple outputs throughout the rotation and reducing the risks associated with farming single commodities
<u>Diversification</u>	Diversification of the local production can benefit the whole rural community by stimulating the local economy, including by creating jobs.
<u>Recreational opportunities</u>	Agroforestry systems can provide recreational opportunities that can benefit the public as well as the landowner. Activities such as hunting, fishing, mountain biking, equestrianism, and rural tourism can diversify income for farmers, while the public can benefit from improved health and enjoyment from agroforestry through sports and wildlife watching.
<u>Landscapes</u>	The visual impact of monocultures of crops or trees is unappealing for many people; integrating trees into agricultural landscapes can increase the diversity and attractiveness of the landscape. Cultural aspects of traditional agroforestry systems, particularly in temperate regions, are often overlooked, despite the long history of woodland and orchard grazing, alpine wooded pastures, pannage, the dehesa and parklands.

Source: [Agroforestry in the European Union](#) (2020 EPRS-European Parliamentary Research Service) and [Agroforestry: Reconciling Production with Protection of the Environment. A Synopsis of Research Literature.](#)

Living Hub “Tuscany” Italy

Within the INNO4CFIs project, one of the LHs is planned in the Tuscany region of Italy and the chosen area is in the province of Grosseto. The manager of the LH is Treedom, with the collaboration of the Italian National Research Council (CNR).

The partners decided to create a diffused hub (in both Montieri and Follonica municipalities) that would include two different climatic zones and agroforestry systems in the same province. This is useful for comparing the possibilities of implementing carbon farming in agroforestry systems in an area as varied in terms of territory and climate as Tuscany and in general Italy. In fact, given the Italian peninsula's great extension in latitude, the climate varies considerably from area to area, being able to identify 6 large climatic regions: Alpine, Po Valley, Adriatic, Apennine, Tyrrhenian, and Mediterranean¹⁷. Moreover, in the same climatic areas, given the considerable variations due to the widespread presence of hilly and mountainous areas, climate differs significantly.

To provide an example, despite the close distance of 40 km, Montieri on a national level is classified as climate zone E (degree days between 1401 and 2100) while Follonica is identified as zone D (degree days between 2101 and 3000)¹⁸.

Another reason to have an extended hub is to implement a carbon farming model in two different agro-production contexts:

- Montieri area (mountainous, meso-Mediterranean) production is based on chestnuts, forestry products, fruit trees, and pastoral activities.
- Follonica area (at sea level, strictly Xero-Mediterranean) production is characterized by olive groves, cereals, fruits, and vegetables.

The two sites of the LH are defined as

¹⁷ C. Blasi, G. Capotorti, R. Copiz, D. Guida, B. Mollo, D. Smiraglia & L. Zavattero (2014) Classification and mapping of the ecoregions of Italy, *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with all Aspects of Plant Biology*, 148:6, 1255-1345, DOI: 10.1080/11263504.2014.985756

¹⁸ Introduced by Presidential Decree No. 412 of 26 August 1993, the classification into climate zones takes into account climate and is calculated on the basis of degree days, i.e. the sum for the various days of the year of the difference between the temperature of the indoor environment and the average outdoor temperature: the higher the result of this operation, the harsher the climate in that area. This is not only a differentiation of the territory according to the geographical position defined by a system of zones ranging from North to South, the subdivision also considers altimetry. Each municipality will belong to a specific climate zone for which specific criteria and timeframes for the use of heating systems apply.

- 1) Montieri, 'Forest area Filicaia' (image 2) intervention area in the Colline Metallifere (Metalliferous Hills);

Figure 2 Montieri location

Figure 3 Filicaia location

- 2) Follonica, 'Santa Paolina' experimental farm managed by the CNR (42.9328° N, 10.7642° E; 17 m above sea level.

Figure 4 Follonica Location

Figure 5 Santa Paolina, Follonica - CNR Location

Living Hub Tuscany, Montieri

For the part of the LH to be installed in Montieri, Treedom will collaborate with local authorities and associations, in particular:

- [the Municipality of Montieri](#);
- [Quercus Association](#) with which it has been working in the area since 2021;
- [Brezzano Cooperative](#).

Treedom and its local partners in 2021 and 2022 managed to revalue a forested area characterised by thousand-year-old chestnut trees.

Cleaning and planting of forest and fruit species were carried out, to promote agroforestry systems in areas of abandonment to have a productive forest, which can provide products all year round, but above all to try to replicate this model also for those areas.

To date, 4,000 plants have been put on the ground, all geolocated, to have a traceability of the activities carried out. Of these, 28% are fruit species, such as chestnut (*Castanea sativa* Mill.), cherry (*Prunus avium* L.), pear (*Pyrus communis* L.), and blackthorn (*Prunus spinosa* L.).

In addition, as side activities, days were held to collect chestnuts and mushrooms, and with cleaning and maintenance, waste wood was obtained and used as material for the manufacture of handicrafts. The area of intervention was in the Filicaie Forest.

Objectives, activities, and expected results of the site.

As a result of increased logging activity, we have observed that the areas subjected to this practice are degrading at twice the rate. By degradation, we mean the loss of the genetic fertility inherent in the forest, which is found both in the soil and in the ecosystem itself. This 'degradation' is due to various climatic factors that are becoming increasingly acute, especially in 'virgin' areas such as the one described in the previous paragraph.

Additionally, the haphazard distribution of rainfall, increasingly rising temperatures, and the absence of woodland cover, lead to the disappearance of all those faunal species that are fundamental for the natural propagation of woodland species in this area.

The objective of the intervention is therefore to extend the already existing agroforestry system for the conservation of the territory and the co-involvement of the territory in agroforestry activities to spread this practice. In addition, the technologies used can provide important information regarding the future use of plants and techniques that can improve the resilience of the land.

Specific objectives:

- Produce, plant, and protect approximately 3,000 native plants divided into two slots;
- Continue the maintenance, cleaning, and promotion of targeted areas during 2021-2022 and future project areas 2023-2025;
- Promote "social" activities that can include a wide range of beneficiaries;
- Apply relevant INNO4CFIs technologies on the site to monitor their application in a relevant environment.

The main activities planned are:

- enlargement of the past intervention in the municipality of Montieri;
- purchase of fruit and forestry plants at the "Vivaio Cerreto di Camaldoli";
- soil and site preparation (cleaning, digging holes, production, transport of plants);
- plants and site maintenance (irrigation and maintenance of the new plants);
- mapping the trees through the Treadom geotagging system;
- performance of measurements and other operations to be identified to experiment with INNO4CFIS technologies and methodologies.

Project area

The ancient Filicaia is an Etruscan Forest that is at least 2000 years old. It is an abandoned coppice and chestnut grove near Travale, a small medieval village in the Colline Metallifere on the border between the province of Siena and Grosseto. Filicaia Forest intervention covers an area of about 3.5 ha to the northwest of Travale. It is situated at an altitude of between 700 and 900 meters above sea level and contains monumental, thousand-year-old trees.

First slot

Figure 7 Bosco Filicaia, Montieri

This pilot portion is divided into two areas:

- Area 1 (orange) develops on the north side of the hill with a 30 m difference in height over a length of approximately 60m, with a slope of 50%. The total area is approximately 1,500 m² (the estimate was made by default).

Planting activities are set, weather permitting, for late February or early March, with the choice mainly of forest and chestnut species. The planting size will be approx. 1.5m x 2m for forestry and 5m x 2m for chestnut trees. This plot will accommodate a total of approximately 500 plants.

- Area 2 (yellow and blue), facing south, develops at the base of the hill, flanked by the le Lame municipal road (easily passable). This plot is almost flat, where no steep slopes are evident, and has a trapezoidal shape. The total area, again estimated by default, is approximately 3880m², this has been divided into 2 sub-areas, with 2 different types of intervention. One measures 1600 m² and the other 2280 m².

Planting activities are set, weather conditions permitting, for the end of February/beginning of March, with the choice mainly of fruit species. The planting size will be approximately 2 x 2, with grafted fruit species (dwarfing rootstock species will be preferred), the type of plants will depend on the availability of the selected nursery. In any case, approximately 1,000 plants. Figure 5. Filicaie, Montieri - Italian Living Hubs (IT02A24, IT02B24, IT02C24)

Second slot

The second slot will be identified during 2024 in the same area of Travale. In this second phase, approximately 1,000 trees of forest and fruit species will be planted.

Figure 8 Filicaie, Montieri - Italian Living Hubs (IT02A24, IT02B24, IT02C24)

Agroforestry Plan

Within the chestnut grove, we plan to plant 2/3 three-year-old chestnut trees of different old varieties.

Planting can be done from November to March, grafting is done from February to March, and the scions are taken in February to March, after storage in a refrigerator or sand. From the chestnuts in planting, we obtain fruit and consequently processed products such as flour and jams.

Along the perimeter of the chestnut grove, we will plant fruit trees and bushes, spacing each tree at least 4 meters apart, creating a 50×50×40 hole fertilised with mature manure and supporting the plant with a chestnut tree stake, 5/6 cm in diameter.

From all the trees we will obtain very important fruit, both for local family consumption and for retail sale through farmers' markets and solidarity purchasing groups.

The intention is to create a processing line for fruits, jams, and dried fruits under the Quercus brand. In addition to the fruits and the environmental and forestry benefits, we will in the future obtain the precious wood that can be used for the small farmer's carpentry projects.

The cultivation method used will be organic biodynamic, the planting of a fruit hedge and fruit trees has multiple agro-environmental benefits: lowering of CO₂ resulting from the planting of the trees, introduction of small animals, insects, fungi, shelter of valuable wood, fruit, visual beauty, and well-being.

The pedoclimatic conditions of the area between Travale and Gerfalco (Cornate mountain range) are excellent, both for the exposure and the substrate (rich in humus), an area rich in springs and sources (source of the Cecina River) to produce fruit.

The total area of 3.5 hectares will be divided into two plots of about one and a half hectares, and we will start planting trees on one of them, after which we will start planting on the second plot the following year. In addition, we have approximately 4,000 square meters of land, also in the same area, formerly an orchard, which we will use exclusively for planting fruit trees of old local native varieties (see table above) of Travale.

Species that will be planted:

Species	Motivation	Utility	Usage	Planting Season
Castanea sativa (Chestnut)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Fresh and processed fruit	Beginning of November to the end of February
Pyrus pyraeaster (Pear)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Fresh and processed fruit	Beginning of November to the end of February
Quercus pubescens (Downy oak)	Biodiversity	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Forest environment maintenance	Beginning of November to the end of February
Quercus cerris (Turkey oak)	Biodiversity	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Forest environment maintenance	Beginning of November to the end of February
Carpinus Orientalis (Black Hornbeam)	Biodiversity	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Forest environment maintenance	Beginning of November to the end of February

Acer Pseudoplatanus (Sycamore)	Biodiversity	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Fresh and processed fruit	Beginning of November to the end of February
Prunus Avium (Cherry)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Fresh and processed fruit	Beginning of November to the end of February
Prunus Domestica (Plum)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Fresh and processed fruit	Beginning of November to the end of February

Beneficiary communities

The community that will benefit from the results of the project is the one that refers to the municipality of Montieri, (about 1185 inhabitants¹⁹) and the village of Travale and the surrounding areas. These are valuable areas obtained through thousands of years of human reclamation, but unfortunately almost completely abandoned to their own devices. The partners involved in this activity and the local authorities want to promote the revaluation of the area, the valorisation of its historical and natural heritage, and the establishment of new agricultural/artisanal businesses to create a social agricultural cooperative that promotes an innovative economy based on the processing of raw materials offered by nature. This project, in its simplicity and transparency, is exportable to any place in need of a similar revaluation intervention. We see the creation, within a hamlet such as Travale, of artistic/craft workshops, of revalued dwellings to be offered to tourists, artists, farmers, artisans, sculptors, and visitors who would like to stay or create stable realities, settling new family units.

INNO4CFIs technological environment applied to the site

Regarding the technologies that will be tested, the Montieri site will be particularly suitable

¹⁹ [Bilancio demografico mensile anno 2022](#) (dati provvisori), su demo.istat.it, ISTAT.

- to the measurements necessary for the elaboration of allometric equations aimed at measuring the CO₂ absorption of the trees planted within the project;
- the experimentation of the TREEO methodology;
- the monitoring through the GIS system of Treadom.

In the course of the project, it will be possible to experiment with further technologies on the site, depending on its evolution. In particular, the Montieri site will be fundamental for the validation of the business model and will be part of the commercial offer of Treadom.

Living Hub Tuscany, Follonica

'Santa Paolina' is an experimental farm (60 ha) of CNR since 1967, dedicated to research, testing and transfer of innovation in agriculture and a platform of biodiversity in several national and European networks (germplasm collections of *Pyrus communis* L., *Diospyros kaki* L.f., *Prunus persica* (L.) Batsch, *Prunus avium* L., *Prunus domestica* L., *Cydonia oblonga* Mill., *Malus domestica* (Suckow) Borkh., *Vitis vinifera* L., *Olea europea* L., *Ulmus* spp., *Cupressus sempervirens* L. and *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. for a total of 2079 varieties and 6700 specimens) focuses to plant genotype characterization (both morphological and molecular), products' value increment (timber, fruit, oil), plant propagation and orchard management techniques.

The soil is sandy-loam (sand 64.2%, silt 16.9% and clay 18.9%) with a low amount of organic matter. The soil belongs to the Piane del Pecora system and was developed on recent alluvial deposits of river and river-pond nature. The depth of the soil was 3 m.

The climate is Mediterranean subarid, with a mean annual air temperature of 16 °C. January is the coldest (9 °C) and July is the warmest month (24 °C). The mean annual precipitation is 650 mm, mostly concentrated in autumn and spring, while summer rainfall is very scarce.

Figure 9 Santa Paolina, Follonica - CNR Location

Objectives, activities and expected results of the site

Overall, the study aims to provide insights into how salt stress or water deficit conditions impact the physiological performance of plants and their carbon storage potential, utilizing a combination of field measurements and modelling approaches.

At the designated site, a comprehensive array of measurements will be undertaken to assess various aspects of plant growth, health, and ecosystem dynamics. These measurements include recording the diameter and height of plants, encompassing both newly introduced species and those already existing within the area. Additionally, the assessment will entail determining plant biomass, which involves quantifying the weight of plants, and leaf mass of the planted species. Furthermore, the study will monitor the survival rate of newly planted species to gauge their adaptability and resilience in the given environment.

Chlorophyll fluorescence, photosynthesis and Soil Plant Analysis Development (SPAD) measurements will be conducted to evaluate the physiological performance of the vegetation, providing insights into their metabolic activity and overall health. We will assess various biophysical plant parameters, including the diameter and height of plants, plant biomass, and leaf mass for each of the 12 selected plants per thesis. These theses will investigate the effects of different irrigation conditions: H₂O+salt, H₂O+salt for relief irrigation, and desalinated H₂O for relief irrigation, across all species involved (Olive and Cypress).

Additionally, we will conduct chlorophyll fluorescence, photosynthesis, and SPAD measurements on three plants per thesis, spanning the same irrigation conditions and species selection as mentioned earlier. The percentage of diseased plants will be documented to assess the prevalence and impact of pathogens or other stressors on the vegetation community.

Moreover, employing a remote sensing approach, leaf hyperspectral reflectance will be analyzed to discern subtle variations in plant physiology performance, aiding in the comprehensive characterization of the vegetation and ecosystem dynamics at the study site. Specific tools will be used, such as Licor 6800, Handy PEA, and SPAD-502Plus for accurate measurement and assessment of the aforementioned physiological parameters.

Project area

The study area consists of:

A) a flat agricultural field of about 1 ha, where the agroforestry demonstration-experimental planting of the INNO4CFIs project with cypress and olive trees will be realized *ex-novo* during winter 2023-2024 (for detailed ecophysiological and productivity in-depth surveys);

Figure 10 Santa Paolina, Follonica - Italian Living Hub (IT01A24)

B) a series of pre-existing fields of olive (4.8 ha) and cypress (3 ha) planted between 1993 and 2015 that will be used for biomass measurements for allometric equations (above-ground carbon storage) under agroforestry conditions.

Figure 11-12 Pre-existing area of olive and cypress trees at Santa Paolina experimental farm of CNR, Follonica. The numbers indicate the year of tree planting.

The agroforestry planting of about 1 ha will consist of 324 olive trees and 192 cypress trees. The planting will be designed according to two irrigation regimes:

- i. 'continuous' precision irrigation and,
- ii. 'relief' irrigation (only when necessary for plant survival).

Both irrigation regimes will be supplied with:

- 1) well water with a certain salinity (caused by the introduction of the saline wedge into the water table by overwatering of agricultural areas) and,
- 2) desalinated water (with a desalinator installed by partner Planet with innovative Mangrove technology, WP3).

Figure 13 Lay-out of the experimental field to be established at S.Paolina CNR exp. farm in winter-spring 2024

As for the plants to be used to make the agroforestry planting, commercial plants purchased from specialized nurseries of 2 years of age in pots about 800-100 cm in size will be used.

Two clonal varieties of both cypress and olive trees will be planted:

- i. *Cupressus sempervirens* var. *stricta*, cv 'Mediterraneo' (CNR clone resistant to bark canker with vigorous growth);
- ii. *Cupressus sempervirens* var. *horizontalis*, cv 'Agrimed No. 1' (CNR clone resistant to bark canker);
- iii. *Olea europaea* cv. 'Leccino' (Internationally widespread and very hardy variety);
- iv. *Olea europaea* cv. 'Canino' (hardy and very high-growing variety).

Irrigation water, both salinized and desalinated, will be distributed via drip irrigation, with irrigation tubes and above-ground drippers. The irrigation system will be connected to the local well, for saline water, and to Planet's Mangrove system, for desalinated water, via a system of tanks, pumps and solenoid valves for the automatic management of irrigation.

After the planting of trees, soil management will be based on the preservation of their physical-chemical and biological fertility, as well as the reduction of water competition between the young trees and herbaceous vegetation. Localized mechanical soil tillage will be carried out at the base of the trees, to reduce the weed vigor. 2 interventions are planned in the vegetative season along the tree rows.

The soil between the rows will be managed using green manure or controlled grassing down techniques, with specific herbaceous cover, to improve the fertility of the soil, increasing the soil organic carbon and also the floristic biodiversity of the herbaceous soil cover, according to agroforestry management for soil protection from erosion, and for carbon and biodiversity farming.

Beneficiary communities

The Santa Paolina Farm is located in direct contact with the town of Follonica (which has about 21,000 inhabitants) and is located in the upper Maremma, an agricultural area par excellence with numerous farms and companies dedicated to the production of quality agricultural products (especially cereals, olive oil, horticultural products).

Santa Paolina has also always been a reference educational installation, where courses, presentations, and meetings are organized on topics of innovation and technology transfer from research to the real market. The CNR experimental farm is a reference hub for both

local and national, as well as international, agriculture, especially for olive tree cultivation, as well for other fruit and tree species.

Furthermore, Follonica has a certain tourist and landscape attractiveness that attracts thousands of people during the spring and summer periods.

All these aspects can be exploited for the promotion of the INNO4CFIs project and for the in-situ demonstration of the technologies applied in an integrated way in this highly replicable context.

INNO4CFIs technological environment applied to the site

The Santa Paolina experimental and demonstrative farm represents the reference site/living hub of the INNO4CFIs project as numerous innovative technologies will be applied and integrated into this agroforestry system.

Living Hub “Castilla y León” Spain

Living Hub Castilla y León, Zamora

Rancho Guareña is an agricultural livestock farm, located in Castrillo de la Guareña (province of Zamora, Spain). The farm portion is approximately 70 ha, irrigated (well 500m deep, water table 90 m deep), with double annual cultivation of winter cereals and corn, to produce fodder for dairy cows. The area is windy and has little rain (only 220 mm per year on average).

The area is in the Northern Mesta, an ancient plateau at 700-900 m above sea level, with a continental Mediterranean climate, very dry due to very low rainfall, similar to a pre-steppe climate. Agricultural activities are possible only thanks to the exploitation of very deep-water tables, which has only recently been made possible by technological progress in centre-pivot irrigation (sometimes called central pivot irrigation), which is a method of crop irrigation in which equipment rotates around a pivot and crops are watered with sprinklers.

The proposal concerning the agroforestry plantation is the result of the expectations of the property and the project requirements and consists of an agroforestry system of about 3 ha (41° 13 '35" N; 5° 19' 29" W; 741 m asl).

Objectives, activities, and expected results of the site

The main objective of the project is the fixation of carbon through agroforestry systems for which a plantation of about 3,000 olive trees has been planned, which will be surrounded by oak and poplar trees, which will protect them from the wind, among other things.

This plantation will benefit from a drip irrigation system to optimise the use of water, thus obtaining optimum conditions for the trees.

In between the olive trees, to obtain the greatest environmental benefit, a drip irrigation system has been designed to allow grasses or cereals such as rye and oats to be grown, optimising space and water use to the maximum and obtaining the greatest possible environmental benefit.

Project area

This area is very disadvantaged. Due to the already harsh climatic conditions of the region (very cold in winter and very warm and dry in summer), we must add that this specific area (Castrillo de la Guareña) has even harsher climatic conditions because of a microclimate related to precipitation.

Figure 14 Climate information for Castrillo de la Guareña.

Furthermore, the land has large unevenness that considerably limits the use of Pivots, which means that this specific plot where the project will be carried out is mainly intended for dryland crops.

The land is fertile, and its little wear makes it suitable for almost any crop, but the unevenness and low rainfall mean it is underused.

However, an underground river of great depth and high flow (the well for water extraction is almost 500 meters deep), allows obtaining an important concession of water that can be used for irrigation.

Despite the water wealth of said underground river, it is a unique opportunity to demonstrate how adequate design and management allow for optimizing the maximum use of natural resources, sustainably, allowing agroforestry work to be carried out even in areas with adverse climates. also fixing carbon and therefore contributing to obtaining great environmental benefits.

Agroforestry Plan

The selected species are Olive trees, of the Arbequina variety, which is the one that best adapts to the climatic characteristics of the area, as well as oaks (*Quercus Pyrenaica*) and some type of poplar yet to be defined. These trees will have a surface drip irrigation system and will be placed leaving a separation of 5 meters between them on one side, and 2 meters on the other, therefore allowing the entry of agricultural machinery and the use between rows for other crops such as cereals or grasses.

Figure 15 Castilla y León - Spanish Living Hub (ES01A24)

The poplars and oaks will be placed around the perimeter of the olive tree cultivation plot to improve their growth, protecting them from the wind and inclement weather. These trees will also have a surface drip irrigation system and the separation will be 5 meters between tree and tree. Approximately 250 trees will be planted between the two species.

Finally, either grasses or some type of cereal such as rye will be grown in between. This plantation will have a buried irrigation system with a high density of drippers that will allow watering depending on the requirements at any given time.

In addition, the entire system will be managed by photovoltaic solar energy, thus contributing to being even more efficient in carbon fixation, reducing the emissions generated by the irrigation process to practically 0.

Beneficiary communities

In general, the entire community is favoured, particularly agriculture and livestock, moving towards more efficient and sustainable agricultural systems, profitable and that contribute decisively to progress.

INNO4CFIs technological environment applied to the site

The technologies used will be:

1. Optimization of the design to protect the species using trees such as oaks and poplars that will contribute decisively to carbon fixation, while protecting the rest of the species in the plantation.
2. State-of-the-art drip irrigation systems that will allow you to make the most of the water, not wasting a single drop. In addition, in this way, the use of the land is optimized.
3. Use of renewable energy systems such as photovoltaic solar energy that will allow the energy that the system will require to be produced so as not to pollute or generate CO₂ in the production process.
4. Use of pumping systems i.e. 3, of the latest generation, which reduce energy consumption to a minimum. Combined with an intelligent irrigation management system.

Living Hub “Wallonia” Belgium

Living Hub Wallonia, Hensies

The site is located in the Western part of Belgium in the ‘Hainaut’ province, in the municipality of ‘Hensies’ in the vicinity of the French border and spreads over an approximate surface of 2ha. The site is also adjacent to a Natura 2000 reserve. The current use of the living hub is partially to act as a buffer layer for the humid zone. The ‘Pommeroeul-Condé’ channel delimits the South border of the site. The site is the property of the regional authorities and is managed both by **ISSEP**, a public scientific institute, and the National Department of Forest (**DNF**).

The following organizations will interact at this Living Hub:

- Novobiom (partner) is responsible for the design and management of the interaction between fungal strains and the plantation.
- The ISSEP (local subcontractor to Novobiom): will support all work related to the trees and the site management (i.e. sourcing of trees, plantation, weed management, soil preparation, watering, etc.). ISSEP's expertise in the field of phytomanagement and environmental metrology, as well as its role as manager of the Hensies site during the WALLPHY project (see below), are essential for the implementation of the Walloon Hub.

Past phytomanagement experiments - WALLPHY project²⁰

Two large-scale experiments were conducted on the site, within the scope of the WALLPHY project. Both trials aimed at valorising the site - a brownfield - using tree planting, while ensuring that no transfer of metallic elements would occur (from the soil to the overall food chain, via plant leaves).

The first experiment was carried out from September 2018 to September 2019. **25.000 willows** have been planted and about a year later, more than 50% of them were dead. The experiment largely failed due to several reasons.

The main lessons learned from the experiment were the following :

- **Pressure from wildlife** in this area is high (rodents have been eating the roots of the seedlings). Therefore **physical protection of the seedling will be required**;

²⁰ <https://dailyscience.be/17/11/2020/des-vegetaux-pour-revaloriser-les-sols-pollues/>

- **Pressure from weeds** is high and largely **reduces access to light and water**. Therefore **weeds management is required** to ensure the proper growth of seedlings;
- During summer, water content can reduce drastically creating **high water stress on young seedlings**. Therefore specific care needs to be taken regarding **watering during the drier season**;
- **Potential phytotoxicity** from metal elements and PAH;
- The site highly differs from a 'classical' agricultural or forestry soil. Therefore planting strategies and species selection must be adapted to the specific strong site constraints.

The second experiment was conducted in October 2019 and its measurements ended in mid-2021 but most of the trees are still on site. This second phase was at a smaller scale and mainly aimed to understand the reasons that led to the failure of the first experiment namely the potential soil toxicity.

Figure 16 Highlights of the planting pattern.

The planting was done with a 'box pattern' in which 16 trees of 6 different species were planted. Figure 16 highlights the planting pattern.

Objectives, activities, and expected results of the site

Objectives

- Planting up to 3000 trees during the project;
- Demonstrate the relevance of adapted phytomanagement practices to facilitate carbon farming at brownfield sites;

- Build a 1st successful use case of carbon farming via phytomanagement practices at brownfields’.

Activities

The core of the activities can be summarized in 3 main points and will unfold in a timely fashion, as follows:

- Tree planting and maintenance;
- Assessing the impact of tree planting on the metallic trace elements and organic contaminants soil content;
- Monitoring of key parameters for proper evaluation of carbon capture as organic matter in trees and soil, carbon mineralization in soil, and the evolution of soil biodiversity.

Preparatory phase (Q2 2024)

In-depth bibliographic research targeting phytomanagement and bioremediation practices, combined with soil carbon sequestration literature.

- The organisation of a series of workshops with experts and local stakeholders from the Natura 2000 zone neighbouring the experimental site will be carried out.

This step will enable the selection of plant species to plant onsite; the selection will exploit the results and key teachings of the WALLPHY project (including the native vegetation from the site as well) to anticipate sourcing trees from suppliers.

Assessment phase (Q2-Q3 2024)

A detailed assessment of the current soil conditions at the site will be undertaken at different depths to identify any significant heterogeneity of the soil substrate. These data will allow the establishment of an experimental plan adapted to the needs specific to the selected species. The data will also be used as a baseline to assess how key flora and soil parameters evolve and their relationship to the undertaken phytomanagement practices.

Implementation & monitoring phase (Q4 2024 till project completion)

Finally, the implementation phase will consist of carrying out tree planting according to the established plan, and its monitoring to evaluate its evolution over time. Other tasks necessary for setting up the Walloon Living Hub (preliminary preparation of the land, tree planting as well as certain monitoring tasks) will be managed by Novobiom.

Project area

Figure 15 highlights the site location and its geometry. The living hub is bordered in the North by a 'Natura 2000' reserve called 'Les Marais d'Harchies' which is a swamp area considered to be a 'humid zone with high biological interest'.

Figure 17 Hensies - Belgium Living Hub (BE01A24)

The site is a former dumping ground for canal cleaning and dredging products. These were discharged by hydraulic backflow. The discharge zone was located on the western end while the eastern end acted as an overflow zone. It is considered that the western zone is covered with an up to 20 m thick layer of sediment.

Soil analyses have been performed in 2018 to determine the level of contamination and other key parameters to understand the soil's global state. The results of these analyses, consistent with an earlier study carried out in 1998, show a silty substrate with a neutral pH, with inorganic levels of Cu, Pb and Zn and several PAHs exceeding threshold values for recreational/commercial use according to the local regulation. The agronomic parameters measured indicate that the substrate is eutrophied, with high levels of N, P, K and Ca as well as organic matter. The sediment consists mainly of clay silt and sandy silt, sometimes mixed with various types of waste, and locally showing traces of hydrocarbons and metals. The sediment layer is highly charged with organic matter ranging from 15% to 20% in mass.

Agroforestry Plan

The proposed agroforestry plan will build on the knowledge acquired during the WALLPHY project. Considering the nature of and local requirement for the site - a marginal site, the phytomanagement practices to be implemented need to differ from agroforestry practices. Instead, the trees to be planted will consist of species which have demonstrated their suitability for the site.

The following tree species are foreseen, according to their shown benefits for the site:

- *Quercus petraea* (oak): tolerance to contaminants;
- *Quercus pubescens* (oak): thermophilic, potentially resistant to global warming;
- *Cornus sanguinea* (dogwood): promoting biodiversity;
- *Euonymus europaeus* (spindle tree): promoting biodiversity, hedge formation;
- *Viburnum opulus* (guelder rose): promoting biodiversity;
- *Salix viminalis* (willow): tolerance to & accumulation of metallic elements;
- *Alnus glutinosa* (alder): tolerance to & accumulation of metallic elements;
- *Populus x canescens* (poplar): fast grower, tolerance to & accumulation of metallic elements.

Foreseen planting strategy

A maximum of 3000 trees will be planted in patches, consisting of small cells (around 16 m² each) with a planting density of less than 1 tree/m².

This planting format allows:

- an optimization of the growth conditions for a few individuals, and ultimately only one, per cell;
- a more effective control of weed competition;
- the protection of each individual against the appetite of rodents thanks to the installation of a sheath.

The plants will be purchased in plugs to avoid drying out of the roots between the delivery and planting dates. For each plant, an acacia stake (2.8/210 cm) will be used as well as a protective sheath in a biodegradable sleeve (60 cm). The surfaces to be planted will be covered with a biodegradable geotextile tarpaulin. Varying cell modalities (mixing of tree species) will be set and planted at a rate of 6 at least repetitions per modality.

Maintenance and monitoring

Novobiom will provide proprietary monitoring devices for the real-time recording of key soil parameters (water content, electrical conductivity, CO₂/O₂, temperature), providing valuable data sets in the scope of soil C and biodiversity monitoring.

Activities relating to site maintenance and monitoring will be performed by ISSEP, with careful attention to water availability/water needs and the collection of soil & tree biomass samples throughout the project: irrigation will thus be punctually set, taking into account weather conditions evolution, data obtained from the soil monitoring system, and seasons.

Beneficiary communities

The foreseen benefits consist in improving the ecological value of the zone. The planting activity will provide a vegetal buffer zone between the canal and the Natura 2000 site, thus expanding the natural habitat for the macrofauna. Ultimately, accounting for biodiversity and carbon sequestration gains could help mainstream the use of phytomanagerial practices at marginal sites, for which no future agricultural and economic development is possible. Indeed, this Living Hub could become a “lighthouse” site for the promotion of carbon farming practices applied to phytomanagement.

INNO4CFIs technological environment applied to the site

Apart from the tree growth methodologies to be applied at all Living Hubs, the following tests will be carried out:

- On-the-ground follow-up/census of survival of the planted trees and extrapolation of above-ground CO₂ sequestration as wood biomass.
- Soil sampling and analyses: for the follow-up of soil physical and chemical parameters, soil microbiome for the assessment of below-ground biodiversity, ecotoxicity tests
- Biomass sampling: for the quantification of the potential presence of contaminants transfer from the soil to the trees’ aerial parts.
- Census of observed fauna and flora species to account for the evolution of above-ground biodiversity.

Remark: it is anticipated that sampling and observation points will be carried out on a trimestrial basis.

Living Hub “Attica” Greece

Living Hub Attica, Agios Georgios-Mandra

The LHs that are planned within the INNO4CFIs project in the Attica region of Greece are situated in the area of Agios Georgios-Mandra approximately 46 km from the city center of Athens. The partners involved in this LH are NTUA along with Planet. NTUA is in charge of all the preparation work and monitoring that will be conducted while Planet will contribute to the technologies to be applied.

Figure 18 Agios Georgios-Mandra, Attica - Greek Living Hub (GR01A24)

The area of Agios Georgios-Mandra is located in the plain sections between two mountain masses with mild climate characteristics. In general, Greece is a country characterized by the typical climatic conditions of the Mediterranean region, with mild and wet winters and warm and dry summers²¹. Despite that, in the different regions of Greece, various climatic subtypes can be identified due to the topography of the country and thus Attica’s climate is best identified as dry when compared to the North and West parts²².

The forest area surrounding the LH was burnt in August of 2021 in a 3-day fire. As a result, the fire left behind a low-value land, as characterized by the locals, that is currently used

²¹ P. Lionello, P. Malanotte-Rizzoli, R. Boscolo, P. Alpert, V. Artale, L. Li, J. Luterbacher, W. May, R. Trigo, M. Tsimplis, U. Ulbrich, E. Xoplaki, 2006, The Mediterranean climate: An overview of the main characteristics and issues, *Developments in Earth and Environmental Sciences*, Elsevier, Volume 4, Pages 1-26, ISBN 9780444521705, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1571-9197\(06\)80003-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1571-9197(06)80003-0).

²² Hellenic National Meteorological Service, 2024, The climate of Greece, accessed on 25/2/2024, through: <http://www.emy.gr/emv/en/climatology/climatology?>

for sparse cultivations of productive trees like olive trees, wild pears and almond trees. The presence of some forestal tree species can also be spotted.

Objectives, activities, and expected results of the site

The fires of 2021 left more than 32000 ha burnt, which by turn, led to severe loss of biodiversity both in flora and in fauna. When it comes to floral biodiversity, fires can cause complete loss of certain species, by harming the plant itself, the seeds and the seedlings²³. Fires can also alter the vegetation of an area with the dominance of species that have a natural regeneration capacity after a fire²³.

Taking the previous information into account, the objective of the intervention is to create an agroforestry system for the restoration and reinforcement of the biodiversity of the territory. An additional advantage would also be the dissemination of the agroforestry practices and their potential in an area like this, within the frames of an effort to spread this practice. Finally, the technologies that will be used can provide important information regarding the future use of plants and techniques that can improve the resilience of the land.

The specific objectives of the site could include the following:

- Restore a part of the land belonging to a fire-struck area;
- Increase/restore the carbon farming potential of the area;
- Enhance biodiversity;
- Create additional value in the area through the production potential of the species that will be used;
- Promote a sustainable and self-sustained (up to a certain point) system of cultivation;
- Promote "social" awareness of agroforestry and activities;

Concerning the main activities that are planned, they are as follows:

- Soil sampling to determine the initial state of the site (which is already done);
- Removal of debris, burnt trees and big rocks from the site area;
- The enclosure of the site with a fence to protect the trees/plants from wild boars found in the area;
- Construction of a water collection basin;
- Determination of the agroforestry plantation scheme;
- Further soil and site preparations for the plantations;

²³ Kalogiannidis S, Chatzitheodoridis F, Kalfas D, Patitsa C, Papagrigoriou A. Socio-Psychological, Economic and Environmental Effects of Forest Fires. *Fire*. 2023; 6(7):280. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire6070280>.

- Purchase of fruit and forestry plants and transportation to the site;
- Plantation;
- Installation of moisture sensors;
- Plants and site maintenance;

Project area

In the following figure (Figure 17) the LH location and its boundaries can be seen. The total space of the study area is 40000 with discussions of expanding it to a total of 50000 acres through extra neighboring land.

Figure 19 Agios Georgios-Mandra, Attica - Greek Living Hub (GR01A24)

The environmental characteristics as described in the beginning are typical of the Mediterranean climate with the area of Attica being a bit drier than the Northern and Western parts of Greece. There is a slight slope present in the site currently, but the exact inclination will be identified by the end of the site preparation works which may negligibly alter it.

The soil in the site is clay (sand 18,28%, silt 35,15% and clay 46,57%) with an average amount of organic matter. The C/N ratio is 17,76 which is considered low (desirable C/N ratio is 25 to 35), leading to high availability of nitrogen for plant uptake but at the same

time greater nitrogen loss^{24,25}. These parameters were all considered for the upcoming agroforestry system establishment, the cultivation practices that will be followed, as well as the plant species selection.

There are not any external sources of water (e.g. water duct) and there are not any water drillings. Thus, a water collection basin will be constructed at the northeast part of the site to collect and store water.

Agroforestry Plan

The planting activities are scheduled to be done at the beginning of May of 2024 (to be confirmed), as the estimated arrival of the plants in the LH is at the end of April of 2024 (to be confirmed). The planting distances are still under discussion, with the current distance being 5×5. The plants that are already decided are olive trees of three varieties (Koroneiki, Breatsera or Manaki, Arbequina) and the rest will depend on the availability of the nursery. The estimated number of plants will approximately be 1,600+ plants.

More specifically, within the site, we plan to establish 1500 olive trees, from the three varieties that were mentioned before. The main olive tree varieties will be Koroneiki and Arbequina, with 700 and 600 pieces respectively, while 200 pieces of the Bratsera or Manaki variety will be included. Koroneiki, Bratsera and Manaki varieties are of Greek origin and therefore adjusted to the Greek climatic conditions and Arbequina is a Spanish variety adjusted to the Mediterranean climate thus it can also survive in Greece. Furthermore, Cypress trees will be added along the perimeter of the site to act as a wind barrier and protect the agroforestry system from extreme events, contributing to the biodiversity at the same time. The variety that was chosen is *Cupressus sempervirens* L. which is native to the Mediterranean region and Greece²⁶.

One of the primary reasons for the selection of these varieties is their adjustment and survival potential in the chosen LH region. Other selection criteria were the long-term addition of value to the land, the carbon removal and the enrichment of the biodiversity of the region. The olives (when the trees enter the productive phase) from the olive trees will

²⁴ Akrotos C.S., Tekerlekopoulou A.G., Vasiliadou I.A., Vayenas D.V., 2017, Chapter 8 - Cocomposting of olive mill waste for the production of soil amendments, Olive Mill Waste, Academic Press, Pages 161-182, ISBN 9780128053140, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805314-0.00008-X>.

²⁵ Brust G.E., 2019, Chapter 9 - Management Strategies for Organic Vegetable Fertility, Safety and Practice for Organic Food, Academic Press, Pages 193-212, ISBN 9780128120606, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812060-6.00009-X>.

²⁶ Caudullo, G., de Rigo, D., 2016. *Cupressus sempervirens* in Europe: distribution, habitat, usage and threats. In: San-Miguel-Ayán, J., de Rigo, D., Caudullo, G., Houston Durrant, T., Mauri, A. (Eds.), European Atlas of Forest Tree Species. Publ. Off. EU, Luxembourg, pp. e01afb4+.

also be harvested, which can be used in olive oil production, which can be used for both local family consumption and retail sale through farmers' markets.

Concerning the annual plants that will be also planted so that we can have an agroforestry system, Vicia plants were considered. More specifically, *Vicia sativa L.* was selected due to the additional value it can add to the LH. The plantation of Vicia is planned to be in rows in the middle of the rows where trees are cultivated. We intend to use this annual plant to solve the quick nitrogen removal problem as this variety is widely used as green manure with their integration into the soil before the end of the cultivation season.

In summary, the species that are considered to be planted are the following:

Species	Motivation	Utility	Usage	Planting Season
<i>Olea europaea</i> var. <i>microcarpa alba</i> (Koroneiki)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Olive oil production	Beginning of May 2024
<i>Olea europaea</i> 'Arbequina' (Arbequina)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Olive oil production	Beginning of May 2024
<i>Olea europaea</i> L. (Bratsera)	Fruit production	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Olive oil production	Beginning of May 2024
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L. (Cypress tree)	Biodiversity	CO2 absorption and raw materials.	Forest environment maintenance	Beginning of May 2024

<i>Vicia sativa L.</i> (Vicia)	Fertilization	Biodiversity and raw materials.	Green manure	April 2024
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The irrigation technique in the site will be drip irrigation, with the origin of the water being from the water collection basin that we will construct. There will not be a specific irrigation scheme as moisture sensors will be installed and thus the irrigation will be applied only when it is necessary, reserving the water sources this way.

In general, we intend to create a semi-self-sustained agroforestry system (some human-made interventions will be needed such as pruning, fertilizing and cultivation/harvest of annual crops) with sustainable production potential and CO2 reduction. The utilization of annual crops for fertilization purposes is a nutrient circular economy practice which reduces the need for additional fertilizers, preserving this way both energy and resources. This system will boost biodiversity (through the introduction of small animals, insects, fungi etc) and in addition to the production and the environmental and forestry benefits, the wood mass production could offer an extra marketable product in the future. Finally, the visual pleasure that the agroforestry system will provide within a fire-struck area could not be left out of the benefits.

Beneficiary communities

The local community that will benefit from this project is Agios Georgios-Mandra, Attica. It is an area that suffered during the summer of 2021 with the fires and as a result, it also experienced a notable land degradation. This project will offer the opportunity to revive a part of this area and restore it, bringing along benefits such as fruit production and in general improvement of productive activities through a sustainable cultivation practice. It will contribute to the restoration and augmentation of biodiversity, something that will change the image of the area and will make the already pleasing landscape more colourful. The improvement of soil health is also a huge plus, as soil melioration work will be applied with the plantation of the trees and the cultivation practices that will be followed will help possibly create and maintain better soil quality. Furthermore, it will work as a source of inspiration for the locals to search for and apply innovative and sustainable cultivation practices. The so-far, overlooked area of Agios Georgios-Mandra, could have the potential to gain some popularity as a result of the dissemination work that is part of the INNO4CFIs project.

INNO4CFIs technological environment applied to the site

The technologies that will be tested in the Attica site will be the following:

- Monitoring of the moisture state of the soil through soil moisture sensors;
- Monitoring through the GIS system of Treedom;
- Measuring the CO₂ absorption of the trees planted within the project through allometric equations;
- Collection and storage potential of water in collection basins on the site;

As in the other sites, through the course of this project, it is possible to include and experiment with other technologies too on the LH.